

Aanvraag

Titel	ReproHub: Enhanced Replicability and Open Science Education for Research with Secondary and Sensitive Data
Aanvrager	dr. H. Datta
Dossiernummer Uw weerwoord is in bewerking	500.040.2559

1 - Application type 1

Toelichting

Please answer the questions in this category when you are referee for type 1 - small projects.

1

Alignment with the aim of the Call for proposals (40%)

Commentaar referent 1

N.A.

Commentaar referent 2

N.A.

Weerwoord

2

Feasibility of the proposal (50%)

Commentaar referent 1

N.A.

Commentaar referent 2

N.A.

Weerwoord

3

How relevant and convincing are the plans to sustain the infrastructure after the project ends, incl. software sustainability (if applicable) (10%)?

Commentaar referent 1

N.A.

Commentaar referent 2

N.A.

Weerwoord

2 - Application type 2

Toelichting

Please answer the questions in this category when you are referee for type 2 - large projects.

1

Alignment with the Call for proposals (40%)

Commentaar referent 1

The authors propose an infrastructure (hub) that aims to improve the state of affairs in data and code availability as well as reproducibility of results. While there is progress on data and code availability - at least in available services, much less in their systematic use - reproducibility arguably remains elusive. Needless to say, both data and code availability and, especially, reproducibility are key for trusted open and transparent science. All of this has also a lot to offer in terms of making science clearer, in terms of what was done how. That said, the infrastructure is particularly relevant to the sciences

that rely on some form of data processing where the processing is formalized in some computing system (code, workflows, or similar). So, not all of research, but a lot and big enough to make it worth it for sure. The authors propose four deliverables / systems, and they all make sense except perhaps ReproRun: I am not sure about the viability of having a centralized system to validate results. Frankly speaking, I would keep this element distributed: offer all code and data in a well documented form (including, at least for scripting environments, the requirements of packages and their versions), but then leave it to consumers to setup the environment. Thing is, ensuring working environments for an arbitrary set of code and data, and this "indefinitely", is tough and comes, thus, likely also with high future maintenance. Notable in terms of deliverables is also that the project not only plans to build a technical infrastructure, but also integrates with the social infrastructure through open educational resources and community engagement offering.

The project itself aligns well with open science principles, too. Most notably, the project aims to build on open source technologies, its outputs FAIR software and data deposited on Zenodo, and a transparent governance structure is planned as well. Building on ODISSEI is a strength.

The access policy is adequate, the limitations for ReproBuddy are surely due to the computing costs of the LLM-based AI tooling, which is fair. That said, these costs are proportional with use: as long as use is not overwhelming, the project could consider being more inclusive toward Dutch institutions, and then address the problem if and when use becomes overwhelming (e.g., having other institutes host their own instance).

The project lists, in two short paragraphs, a large number of international systems, from the national ODISSEI to the international SSHOC, EOSC, CODECHECK, etc. That's a long list, but unfortunately it is not clear what is integrated how and where more concretely. For instance, ReproHub's tools will be made discoverable through the EOSC, yes, but how? Through a national / thematic EOSC Node, which one, and how is this done technically? To my understanding, many of these questions have no clear answer. I am of course mindful that all of this can hardly be made more explicit here with a word count of 200. In light of this constraint, I would thus argue that the authors do have a strategy for integration in the international ecosystem in that they are aware of the ecosystem and possible integrations.

Commentaar referent 2

a) Solid vision that spreads across relevant fields of activities (integration, education, infrastructures); in-line with the aim of the call.

b)

- Support in making research more reproducible and in verification of reproducibility. This answers an important need of the research community.

- Discovery across all types of research outputs - highly relevant - using a browser plugin.

(Important limitation: I am not a member of the social sciences community.)

c) The proposal shows a good understanding of Open Science principles and touches on most of the relevant aspects.

In some instances, the term "replication" is used, seemingly interchangeable with reproduction ("replication packages", "replication event", project title). It is not clear if this is an oversight or intentional. It is generally understood that reproduction and replication are distinct concepts.

d) No - everything seems to be planned as openly available.

e) Only limitedly: documentation and discovery are mentioned, but no technical integrations.

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2

Feasibility of the proposal (40%)

Commentaar referent 1

Question a) is hard to evaluate. The authors did their best to present the project plan under the constraints of word count. The plan is clearly structured in WPs matching the four deliverables and each WP is nicely structured and contains, in a very succinct manner, key tasks and deliverables. However, the brevity makes it hard or even impossible to determine how realistic the plan truly is. For instance, WP 1 plans to build an AI-assistant and the tasks are those I would also expect, e.g. engineer prompts and validate the output. This is all plausible, but it is so superficial that it is impossible to understand how the authors intend to implement this. For instance, what does "improve reproducibility packages" entail? How would a typical prompt look like? I understand that an open source LLM will be used: Any preliminary insights on performance for the task? Again, I am conscious of the word count limit, and as such I would say that the project plan is well laid out, but for a large project as this one in particular the plan lacks detail.

Team composition is very good and covers excellent technical expertise in infrastructure development as well as good

research field and methodology expertise.

Risk management is reasonable, the mitigation strategies are good. Personally, I would rate the risks around LLMs higher, especially given that there is no evidence in the proposal for how well the (open source) LLMs to be used perform for the tasks at hand. Given the information in the proposal, it may be that ReproBuddy will perform so bad that it won't serve the purpose - it's impossible to tell, I think.

The main authors have a large share of the budget, meaning they will be carrying out the work themselves, to a large extent. An additional RSE with 2.8 FTEs is to be hired. This composition is good, the fact that the main authors will be carrying out the bulk of the work is also refreshing. More concerning is the relatively long list of people involved only with minimal effort, still requesting in total about 500 k€ (a third of the total budget and almost 40% of total personnel costs). This is quite a share of the budget that is spread widely and thinly and, depending on management, there is a risk this share of the budget will underperform in output compared to the share that goes to the core group. That said, it really depends on management and the effective and efficient integration of the people and their expertise and time in the project. Hence, it is a potential risk not a necessary outcome.

Building on ODISSEI is arguably the biggest factor that is likely to drive substantial impact. Integration with journals and peer review is interesting, but to my personal (albeit somewhat limited) experience rather hard and a winding road. That said, I guess it strongly depends on the connections of the team to journals and publishers. Stakeholders other than academia are mentioned, including journalists, policymakers, and the general public. However, how these stakeholder groups will benefit remains largely unclear, except with the abstract note that "society will benefit from trusted verification of research results" - which is arguably true, but it remains vague. Also, how else will the proposed infrastructure impact stakeholder groups?

Commentaar referent 2

a) The browser plugin is a good idea to integrate seamlessly in everyday research work. Using journals as multipliers is also a good approach, though the collaboration only lists example journals without concrete collaboration plans or past collaborations mentioned.

However, the impact plan, even with the considerable funding, is very ambitious and the "scalable impact" reaching "global" stage seems to go too far, even though the step-wise approach starting with a local user group is convincing.

The agile development approach is reasonable, though it is unclear why the first 1.5 years are called "prototyping". The three development phases seem to counteract an agile approach where one wants to reach integration and embedding (unsure what precisely that means) as soon as possible.

The four work deliverables seem indeed to be independent products under independent "brands". This can be good, because deliverables can reach their goals independently, but also makes one wonder of missed opportunities for the products to connect. Will reproducibility packages built with ReproBuddy be better/easier to be checked with ReproRun?

Open questions:

- What are the "reproducibility guidelines" that ReproBuddy will be based on? Existing, established one, or new ones?
- What is a "successful" validation by ReproRun? What kinds of results (statistics? plots? output data?) can be validated?
- What kind of input will ReproRun "understand"? A Makefile, a Quarto file? Knowing this now is crucial to be able to appeal to users with diverse workflows. Considering the goal of an automated workflow, providing Docker templates and integration into an existing platform seems pretty straightforward and mundane.
- Given the current state of the EOSC projects, it remains unclear what an "adoption by EOSC" entails.

b) As presented in the proposal, the staff can build on established collaborations and covers the required roles and skill sets.

Not a single full time staff, esp. no RSE, does add the challenge of scheduling development tasks with other obligations. While this reflects reality of academic software development, it is still introducing uncertainty.

c) The list of risks overall is reasonable and the mitigation strategies suitable. I only struggle with the estimated "low likelihood" and "medium impact" of the dependency on external parties adoption. This is a huge risk (no adoption = no users) and the likelihood, for three so different tools, seems too optimistic. I suggest to revisit the heavy developer focus in the planned budget and consider outreach and communication for a proper position within the project.

d) The overall budget is understandable and sound, no relevant large items are missing, with the exception of a person to focus on user support and outreach.

e) The plans to research impact within the domain are reasonable, especially the direct collaboration with local

communities and users, as well as the accessibility via an SSO mechanism. If the practices of these communities can be steered towards the developed deliverables, the positive impact on reproducibility is very high.

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3

3. How relevant and convincing are the plans to sustain the infrastructure after the project ends, including software sustainability (if applicable)? (20%)

Commentaar referent 1

The sustainability plans in this proposal are excellent and one in a kind. It is actually unusual (in my experience as a proposal reviewer) to see such detailed sustainability plans at the cost of detailed project plans. I am used to the other model, large implementation plans and little clues about sustainability. Given word count limits here, too, there is hardly anything to say about the excellent sustainability plans proposed here. I appreciate particularly also details such as software versioning on GitHub as well as release depositions on Zenodo for long-term archiving. This clearly shows that the authors are well aware of what sustainability entails.

Perhaps two additional comments:

- I am unclear what cataloguing software in the EOSC means. In OpenAIRE research graph? The EOSC Portal used to have a marketplace as a catalogue, but this was phased out. At this point, I am not sure what exactly the EOSC catalogue is. But, yes, I presume there will be one again (or, if there is already one, I am obviously not aware of the latest developments).
- Authors could consider publishing a paper about the software, in addition to archiving stable releases on Zenodo.

Commentaar referent 2

I have a mixed opinion about the sustainability of the proposal.

The software management plan ticks all the boxes and complies with good software development practices.

ReproRun being uptaken by EOSC? I find this to be a political dimension that is hard to plan.

For a proposal of this size, I would hope for a diversification of the supporting universities/stakeholders.

Mention "widely adopted technologies and avoid niche dependencies" - would be very interesting to learn more concrete details there (some software libraries are mentioned in other parts of the proposal). The proposal lacks a distinction between reuse/extension of base software and own codebase/new contributions.

The formal commitment by the infrastructure ODISSEI is a considerable factor that should ensure sustainability - I assume a corresponding letter is/can be provided.

While the post-project staffing needs seems solid, I do wonder how the multiple part-time positions will be filled and the risk of staff being torn between diverse responsibilities could negatively affect the long-term operations.

On recovering future costs, the proposal remains vague. Do any collaborations with journals already exist? Even on a 4 year schedule, building these relations is hard to schedule ahead. I agree this is a very important avenue to ensure long term maintenance, but also a challenging one.

While I have no objections of having all WPs run across all months (any Gantt project chart does not survive contact with reality) it remains a bit too unclear how they are connected, or how the different tools may support each other.

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Overall

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